

Farming systems

Efficacy of insecticides against overwintering rice stem borer (SB) larvae

Ehsan-ul-Haq and C. Inayatullah, Entomological Research Laboratories, National Agricultural Research Centre, Islamabad, Pakistan

Recent adoption of no-tillage wheat after rice has led to concern about increased survival of stem borers between rice crops. Three stem borers hibernate in the

rice stubble: *Scirpophaga incertulas*, *S. innotata*, and *Sesamia inferens*.

We tested the efficacy of chlorpyrifos granules 5% wt/wt at 25 kg/ha, chlorpyrifos 40 EC at 2.5 liters/ha, carbofuran 3% wt/wt at 25 kg/ha, and diazinon granules 10% G at 25 kg/ha against SB in no-tillage and conventional-tillage wheat after rice during 1988-89 at Kot Mubarak. Plot size was 5 × 8 m, with three replications.

Insecticides were applied with irrigation water on 21 Feb and 13 Mar.

Larval mortality was recorded on 12 Mar and 5 Apr.

Both insecticides and tillage system had a significant effect on larval mortality. Average larval mortality was 66 ± 26% in no-tillage plots and 78 ± 29% in conventional-tillage plots. Larval mortality was high in conventional-tillage wheat because the stubbles were broken open, increasing larval contact with insecticides.

Larval mortality with insecticides was 80-84%. ■

Studies on rice-based cropping systems

K. Jayakumar and RM. Alagappan, Agronomy Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Annamalai University, Annamalainagar 608002, Tamil Nadu, India

Rice is the principal crop in the tail end of Cauvery delta, Tamil Nadu. We conducted a field experiment with six rotations: rice - black gram, rice - green gram, rice - cowpea, watergrass - watergrass, rice - soybean, and rice - sesame.

The soil was clay (50% clay, 19% silt, and 31% sand) low in available N (228 kg/ha), medium in available P (21.57 kg/ha), and high in available K (348.6 kg/ha). The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications.

Economics of rice-based cropping systems for Tamil Nadu.

Rotation	Grain yield (t/ha)			Net profit (\$/ha)	Benefit:cost ratio
	Crop 1	Crop 2	Total		
Rice - black gram	5.9	0.7	6.6	739	2.3 1
Rice - green gram	5.8	0.6	6.3	634	2.00
Rice - cowpea	5.7	0.4	6.1	560	1.76
Watergrass - watergrass ^a	8.9	6.5	15.4	140	1.04
Rice - soybean	5.5	0.6	6.1	586	1.83
Rice - sesame	5.6	0.1	5.7		489 1.58

^aForage yield.

Fertilizer was applied at 100:22:62 kg NPK/ha to rice and 90:20:37 kg NPK/ha to watergrass; no fertilizer was applied to black gram, green gram, cowpea, soybean, and sesame. The rice crop was irrigated; the other crops were rainfed. No protection against pests or diseases was necessary.

Highest grain yield was with rice - black gram, followed by rice - green gram and lowest with rice - sesame (see table). Watergrass - watergrass yielded more forage.

The highest net return and benefit:cost ratio was with rice - black gram, the lowest with watergrass - watergrass. ■

Farmers' herbicide application method in Koronadal, South Cotabato, Philippines

L. E. Estorninos, Jr., and K. Moody, IRRRI

Some farmers in Koronadal, South Cotabato, Philippines, use chicken feathers attached to the end of a wooden stick to apply herbicides. The feathers are dipped into concentrated herbicide, which has been poured into a coconut shell. The herbicide is applied by swinging the stick in a side-to-side motion, similar to swinging the lance of a conventional sprayer. The farmers make the stick to deposit the herbicide in the water.

Farmer applying herbicide in Koronadal, South Cotabato, Philippines.

The photograph shows a farmer using this method to apply butachlor (approximately 1 liter, equivalent to 600 g ai/ha) in transplanted rice.

The farmers say the technique is easy to use, they need not buy or borrow a sprayer, and water to fill the sprayer is not needed. ■